

Deep Learning Methodologies for Non-Destructive Evaluation of Cultural Heritage Structures

Anindita Kundu Mondal¹, Dr. Aruna Chamatkar²

¹Research Scholar, Department of Computer Science, RTMNU University, Nagpur, Maharashtra, India.

²Associate Professor, MCA Department, Kamla Nehru Mahavidyalaya, RTMNU University, Nagpur, Maharashtra, India.

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 02 March 2026	Non-destructive evaluation (NDE) of heritage structures is essential and necessary for effective conservation with long-term preservation. In recent years, deep learning techniques with the help of computer vision have emerged as powerful tools for analyzing and detecting damage in historic monuments and its structural assessment. This methodological review examines progression from classical machine learning approaches to convolutional neural networks, generative adversarial networks, and attention-based models is analyzed. This paper also highlight their roles in damage detection and monument recognition. It compares classification and segmentation techniques based on their methodological strengths, limitations and suitability for various heritage sites.
Corresponding Author: Anindita Kundu Mondal	The discussion covers key challenges such as data scarcity and practical application of these methods in real world scenario. Future research directions are outlined to help develop reliable and interpret able AI-based tools for heritage conservation.
KEYWORDS: Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix, Convolution Neural Network, Image Classification, Image Segmentation, Object Detection.	

I. INTRODUCTION

This Cultural heritage structure including archaeological sites, historic buildings, palaces, forts and religious monuments represent invaluable records of human history, artistry and their cultural identity. Preserving these heritage buildings is essential, as they serve as tangible links to the past, promoting cultural inheritance and national identity. Conservation of these monuments is challenging aspect due to their natural aging, environmental exposure, weather conditions, urbanization, tourism and vandalism. These are the factors that affect the historic monument condition. Reliable assessment of structural condition and material degradation is therefore essential for effective conservation planning.

The traditional inspection approach proceeded by archaeological survey, take the images and analyse with the previous images and then predict the monument degradation. However, traditional inspection techniques often involve invasive or contact based procedures that may damage to susceptible heritage materials. As a consequence, non-destructive evaluation (NDE) methods have emerged as an

essential pillar of modern cultural heritage conservation practices.

Primary computational approaches relied on classical machine learning (ML) techniques, such as support vector machines and classifiers, combined with handcrafted features extracted from visual data [1] [2]. In recent years, AI technologies can classify the monument structure and also increasingly employed in heritage conservation to detect specific structural issues such as cracks, weathering and erosion with the help of some tools like image recognition, drones, and sensor networks. As conservation is an ongoing and dynamic process, these AI models must continuously monitor environmental factors, such as weather patterns and pollution and predict the long-term stability of monuments.

The inception of deep learning, specifically convolutional neural networks (CNNs), represented a paradigm shift in automated heritage analysis by enabling end-to-end feature learning directly from raw images. CNN based architectures have achieved notable improvements in tasks such as crack detection, surface deterioration assessment, monument recognition, and damage segmentation [3][4][5][6][7]. Advanced region-based and segmentation frameworks,

including Mask R-CNN and UNET, have further enhanced the localization and quantification of damage patterns in historic masonry, stone monuments, and concrete structures [8] [9].

Consequently, generative adversarial networks (GANs) models expanded the methodological landscape by addressing data scarcity and anomaly detection challenges commonly encountered in heritage applications. GAN-based approaches have been employed for synthetic data generation, image enhancement, and unsupervised defect detection, improving model robustness under limited training data conditions [10].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Researchers have been working on Image classification and segmentation technique of deep learning for various monument images. After classification and segmentation, the damage will be detected automatically and this will help for further preservation process.

Global features like non-linearity edges, textures, corners and color was detected using Convolutional layer. It provides accurate detection and classification of monuments and real time monitoring [11].

The paper [12], demonstrates architectural landmark by taking picture and learn about it in terms of its historical and cultural significance, and also know more about how various design styles have diverged or amalgamated to give rise to these architectural wonders around us.

According to [13], a deep learning based approach developed to automatically identify Indian heritage monuments from images. Detection model includes: RCNN, SPPNET, FAST RCNN, FASTER RCNN and Feature Pyramid Network. CNN can achieve high accuracy and performance on a diverse and challenging dataset of Indian Monuments.

Alongside architectural advancements, the nature of computer vision tasks in cultural heritage conservation has diversified. Classification approaches are commonly used for identifying monument and its present condition, i.e., damage type recognition [14] [13], here detection methods mainly focus on structural elements or locating defects, and segmentation techniques describe measurement of deterioration regions, i.e., depth of the defect [15] [16]. The effectiveness of each task and methodology depends strongly on different factors such as heritage material, soil quality, weathering conditions and conservation objectives. However, much of the existing research focuses on application specific outcomes, with limited comparison of the strengths, weaknesses, and overall suitability of different learning approaches.

Recently, Rank-R tensor based learning model is used to identify and classify material defect on Heritage monuments. By modelling global dependencies and selectively weighting relevant patterns, attention mechanisms offer improved robustness and accuracy on hyper spectral images, multi-material structures, and ultra-fine degradation scenarios [17]

[18]. As compare to classic CNN methods, these models have shown promising performance in applications such as multi-sensor data fusion and large-scale monument inspection [19] [20].

To address this gap, this paper presents a methodological review of various deep learning techniques applied to the non-destructive evaluation of cultural heritage structures. Tracing the evolution from traditional machine learning to modern CNNs and attention-based mechanisms, this paper offers a comparative analysis of their application in heritage-related classification, detection, and segmentation tasks. Furthermore, it presents a critical discussion on the suitability of these paradigms for diverse materials and conservation contexts, ultimately establishing a structured guide for selecting appropriate AI methods in cultural heritage.

III. METHODS

Computer vision techniques increases the use of damage detection of historical monuments. The methods of Grey level Co-occurrence matrix, Convolution Neural Network and Deep learning algorithms are used in different historical monuments for Non-Destructive Evaluation of Cultural Heritage Structures.

For detecting the damage on historical monuments, the first step comprises of the cleaning of the data and feature extraction.

A. GLCM (Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix)

GLCM uses early computational approaches relied on classical machine learning (ML) techniques architecture for historical monuments involves pre-processing, GLCM computation, texture feature extraction and classification.

Fig 1: GLCM architecture for detecting historical monuments

A GLCM based system for analysing historical monuments starts by collecting images of the structures. Images are then pre-processed, which includes resizing of image, removing noise and converting them from RGB to grayscale image. This will clear the texture details. The Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM) is then calculated at different angles, to understand how pixel intensities relate to one another in space. This matrix then help to find the key texture features such as contrast, homogeneity, energy and correlation which are extracted and combined into a feature vector. This feature set are fed to traditional machine learning models like Support Vector Machines (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN), or Random Forest for classifying monument surfaces, i.e., for identifying whether they are damaged or undamaged or facing specific issues like cracks or weathering.

An early computational approach such as support vector machines and GLCM, combined with handcrafted features extracted from visual data to create content based image classification by converting feature vector of the images and classify using SVM [1] [2]. As these methods proved initial success in monument classification and material analysis, but their performance was often limited by weathering variations and poor generalization across diverse heritage contexts.

GLCM method, were used to find different angles between the pixels of the image. And from that feature extraction, weathering recognition on monuments of fresh rocks and due to eight different weathering types was done [7].

The objective of finding moss and crack damage in Rock structures for geo- mechanical preservation was developed a non-destructive deep learning model using GLCM and K-means segmentation that can automatically detect, classify, and evaluate two major types of monument decay: moss growth and crack damage [21]. These methods provided decay assessment, damage categories and damage indices to support scientific conservation and restoration planning.

To preserve cultural heritage structure of various temples and monuments of Tamil Nadu, LBP, Luminance and MLNN provides better accuracy, recall, precision and F-score than Luminance and SVM [22]. Here collected images from various temples were pre-processed and fused with local binary pattern and Luminance.

Again, canny detected edge was combined with brightness of the image that improves PSNR (Power signal to noise ratio) than the conventional method. [23].

B. Convolution Neural Network (CNN)

CNN follows a systematic flow from taking raw images as input and convert it into final prediction. In CNN the RGB images of monument surfaces are first fed to an input layer and usually resized to 224×224 pixels. The input image then passes through multiple convolution layers with very small kernels (such as 3×3) that automatically extract major features like edges, cracks, discoloration, texture irregularities and surface discontinuities. Each convolution layer is followed by a ReLU activation function to introduce

non-linearity and improve learning of complex damage patterns and max-pooling layers are used to reduce spatial dimensions while preserving critical features. As the network goes deeper, it learns higher-level representations of structural damage. The extracted feature maps are then converted into one-dimensional vector and fed into fully connected layers. Finally, the output layer uses a sigmoid function used to predict the binary damage detection, i.e., damaged or undamaged or a softmax function for multi-class classification for different damage types such as cracks, erosion, or surface breakage.

Fig II: CNN architecture for detecting damage in historical monuments

The CNN methods can be distributed in three categories: for image classification, for object detection and to find image segmentation.

1) Image Classification: CNN methods used for historical monument image classification include AlexNet, VGGNet, ResNet, Inception, DenseNet, MobileNet, and EfficientNet. Regarding damage identification of masonry historic structures based on the sliding window algorithm, training and validation based on Alexnet and GoogleNet was done, the wall samples were tested and three types of damage: spall, crack, and efflorescence, were quickly and effectively identified. [3].

According to [6], while using various DL technique for mobile historic landmark recognition, comparing between VGGNet, ResNet and DenseNet, the highest F1 score was calculated for DenseNets.

According to [24], the author created a database of historical places of Pune to find construction age, type, colour, shape and size of monument. Images were collected using Samsung Galaxy M32 with 64 MP camera which was first preprocessed, then using feature extraction they got image classification. Using image restoration model every images were restored properly.

ResNet V2 model was another image classification method of CNN used to detect defect like cracking, flaking, erosion and salt efflorescence in Isfahan historical bridges [16]. Using DL methods, extensive database of defects in

historical structures can be prepared that can help to preserve cultural heritage.

Another method for CNN that can be used for image identification and classification is VGG16. This model helps to find accuracy and loss values between training and validation of the model. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves are used to assess the performance of diagnostic tests and machine learning algorithms [25].

II) Object Detection: CNN methods used for object detection of historical monuments include R-CNN, Fast R-CNN, Faster R-CNN, Mask R-CNN, YOLO, SSD, and RetinaNet.

Mask RCNN could also be applicable to assess other damage types like spalling, efflorescence, segregation and corrosion [4]. The model was then trained with labelled examples of damage categories, Mask R-CNN can locate the damage in parallel, classify its type, and accurately segment the affected area, supporting detailed condition assessment and conservation planning.

Another study [26], Mask R-CNN algorithm used to detect and map the deterioration observed in the Gumusler archaeological site. Model were tested on: 2 outdoor images (wide & oblique angles) 2 indoor image, showing frescoes and interior walls, where ResNet was the backbone and applied with the Mask R-CNN. They developed a model that automatically detects and maps deteriorations (biological colonization, contour scaling, crack, higher plant, impact damage, microkarst, missing part) and restoration interventions using the Mask R-CNN algorithm, which has recently come to the fore with its feature of recognizing small and large-sized objects.

As far as moist area is concerned, the model of ResNet101 and FPN provides highly accurate outcomes, unlike the predictions for biological colonization, which are not as much accurate [15].

Another method of object detection is YOLO. Identification of the type of building using YOLO algorithm, [14], determined typology of buildings using façade images and identified separately morphological and structural elements of each period.

A thorough investigation [27], of the effect of camera altitude, data balance and pre-trained weights on model performance finds that models trained and tested on videos taken from similar altitude on videos taken from different altitudes. Models trained on balanced training subset with pre-trained weights from VOC outperforms other models.

III) Image Segmentation: CNN methods used for image segmentation of historical monuments include U-Net, FCN, DeepLabv3+, Mask R-CNN, HRNet, and FPN.

Authors of this paper [5], used computer vision with Unet to detect the concrete cracks. They used U-Net based concrete crack detection method which was compared with DCNN-based method, and U-Net is found to be more elegant than DCNN with more robustness, more effectiveness and more accurate detection.

The study of Great Wall of China in respect to computer vision was done by [28]. The GreatWatcher system, based on MCS techniques and a deep learning algorithm, was developed in this study, focusing on big data collection and damage detection for the Great Wall.

Another study [19], extract the knowledge coming from the typical analysis of B-Scan radargrams, GPR software can convert the radargrams in depth scaled tomographies. The user may then either fine tune the velocity models, or alternatively use these results to identify the required features in the examined structure and assess its layering or state of preservation.

Use of HRNet architecture with SRF module and UE module is another discovery for image segmentation [29]. To detect anatomical landmarks from radiological images, which is able to model spatial and anatomical relationship features between landmarks, HRNet shows high accuracy and better robustness comparing with existing methods.

For detecting Indian monuments of Karnataka and Rajasthan using DL methods [30], two models were simultaneously used: Pix2Pix GAN Model where encoder-decoder form by Unet generator and PatchGAN discriminator were used and BiConvLSTM (BICP2P) Gan Model, where encoding path retains higher- resolution feature maps and decoding path gains by extracting semantic information. The result they got that BICP2P is more efficient than Pix2Pix Gan Model.

All title and author details must be in single-column format and must be centered. Every word in a title must be capitalized. Email address is compulsory for the corresponding author.

IV. HERITAGE PRESERVATION APPLICATIONS

Monument preservation is the need of the era to secure our heritage. It is one of the most emerging application of deep learning. Automatic detection system supports the systematic documentation of historic structure over time, by generating accurate visual records that help in planning, conservation and restoring the monument for long time. The technology blend of computer vision with deep learning, helps to carry records of continuous monitoring of monuments, identify early sign of deterioration or sometimes the depth of the degradation also.

Also for Monument detection technologies, after introducing the use of drone and satellite imagery, provide crucial insights into weathering risks, including vegetation overgrowth and flooding, that endanger heritage sites. The blending of deep learning tools improves the preservation workflows, thus enabling a proactive, data-driven approach to heritage management and sustainability.

V. CONCLUSION

The most essential stage of conservation and preservation of historic monuments is detection of defect in prior. The computer vision with deep learning tools support the detection techniques that helps to restore the monuments for

long term. To guide future AI-driven initiatives in cultural heritage conservation, this review systematically analyzes the shift from classical approaches to advanced CNNs and attention models. It outlines the applicability of these methods in detection, segmentation, and classification, while critically evaluating their limitations across various materials, offering a structured framework for informed methodology selection.

REFERENCES

- Bhatt, M. S., & Patalia, T. P. (2017). Indian monuments classification using support vector machine. *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, 7(4), 1952. [10.11591/ijece.v7i4.pp1952-1963](https://doi.org/10.11591/ijece.v7i4.pp1952-1963)
- Mesanza-Moraza, A., García-Gómez, I., & Azkarate, A. (2020). Machine learning for the built heritage archaeological study. *Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage (JOCCH)*, 14(1), 1-21 <https://doi.org/10.1145/3422993>
- Wang, N., Zhao, Q., Li, S., Zhao, X., & Zhao, P. (2018). Damage classification for masonry historic structures using convolutional neural networks based on still images. *Computer-Aided Civil and Infrastructure Engineering*, 33(12), 1073-1089. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mice.12411>
- Kim, B., & Cho, S. (2019). Image-based concrete crack assessment using mask and region-based convolutional neural network. *Structural Control and Health Monitoring*, 26(8), e2381 <https://doi.org/10.1002/stc.2381>
- Liu, Z., Cao, Y., Wang, Y., & Wang, W. (2019). Computer vision-based concrete crack detection using U-net fully convolutional networks. *Automation in Construction*, 104, 129-139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2019.04.005>
- Bayram, B., Kılıç, B., Özoğlu, F., Erdem, F., Bakirman, T., Sivri, S., & Delen, A. (2020). A deep learning integrated mobile application for historic landmark recognition: A case study of Istanbul. *Mersin Photogrammetry Journal*, 2(2), 38-50.
- Hatir, M. E., Barstuğan, M., & İnce, İ. (2020). Deep learning-based weathering type recognition in historical stone monuments. *Journal of Cultural Heritage*, 45, 193-203. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2020.04.008>
- He, K., Gkioxari, G., Dollár, P., & Girshick, R. (2017). Mask R-CNN. In *Proceedings of the IEEE international conference on computer vision* (pp. 2961-2969). [10.1109/ICCV.2017.322](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCV.2017.322)
- Wang, N., Zhao, X., Zou, Z., Zhao, P., & Qi, F. (2020). Autonomous damage segmentation and measurement of glazed tiles in historic buildings via deep learning. *Computers-Aided Civil and Infrastructure Engineering*, 35(3), 277-291. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mice.12488>
- Liu, Y., Wang, Y., & Liu, C. (2023). A deep-learning method using auto-encoder and generative adversarial network for anomaly detection on ancient stone stele surfaces. *arXiv*. DOI:[10.48550/arXiv.2308.04426](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2308.04426)
- K. Kishan, G. Navya, B. Abhilash Reddy, A. Pranith (2025). Advance legacy Monuments Categorizing using deep learning. *International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering Technology and Science*, 7(1), 4728-4734.
- Jyoti Paul, A., Ghose, S., Aggarwal, K., Nethaji, N., Pal, S., & Dutta Purkayastha, A. (2021). Machine Learning Advances aiding Recognition and Classification of Indian Monuments and Landmarks. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv-2107. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2107.14070>
- Shelke, S. M., Shahale, K. A., Pathak, I. S., Lunge, D. V., Sangai, A. P., & Vyawahare, H. R. (2023). Indian heritage monuments identification using deep learning methodologies. *SSGM Journal of Science and Engineering*, 1(1), 52-56.
- Siountri, K., & Anagnostopoulos, C. N. (2023). The classification of cultural heritage buildings in athens using deep learning techniques. *Heritage*, 6(4), 3673-3705. <https://doi.org/10.3390/heritage6040195>
- Bruno, S., Galantucci, R. A., & Musicco, A. (2023). Decay detection in historic buildings through image-based deep learning. *VITRUVIO-International Journal of Architectural Technology and Sustainability*, 8, 6-17 DOI:[10.4995/vitruvioijats.2023.18662](https://doi.org/10.4995/vitruvioijats.2023.18662)
- Karimi, N., Valibeig, N., & Rabiee, H. R. (2024). Deterioration detection in historical buildings with different materials based on novel deep learning methods with focusing on isfahan historical bridges. *International Journal of Architectural Heritage*, 18(6), 981-993. DOI:[10.1080/15583058.2023.2201576](https://doi.org/10.1080/15583058.2023.2201576)
- Tzortzis, I. N., Rallis, I., Makantasis, K., Doulamis, A., Doulamis, N., & Voulodimos, A. (2022). Automatic inspection of cultural monuments using deep and tensor-based learning on hyperspectral imagery. *arXiv*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2207.02163>
- Yan, C., Cheng, Y., Zhang, Y., Yu, H., Huang, J., & Yan, H. (2024). Study on the applicability of deterioration detection techniques for sandstone heritage in multi environment using MLP-Attention model. *International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, 48(4),541-547.

<https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLVIII-4-2024-541-2024>

19. Alexakis, E., Lampropoulos, K., Doulamis, N., Doulamis, A., & Moropoulou, A. (2022). Deep Learning approach for the identification of Structural Layers in Historic Monuments from Ground Penetrating Radar Images. *Scientific Culture*, 8(2). DOI:[10.5281/zenodo.5772558](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5772558)
20. Wang, X., Cheng, Y., Zhang, R., Zhang, Y., Huang, J., & Yan, H. (2024). Non-destructive assessment of stone heritage weathering types based on machine learning method using hyperspectral data. *International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, 48(1), 713–719. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLVIII-1-2024-713-2024>
21. Ramani, P., Reji, V., Sathish Kumar, V., Murali, G., & Kurhade, A. S. (2025). Deep Learning-Based Detection and Classification of Moss and Crack Damage in Rock Structures for Geo-Mechanical Preservation. *Journal of Mines, Metals & Fuels*, 73(3). <https://doi.org/10.18311/jmmf/2025/47760>
22. Perumal, R., & Venkatachalam, S. B. (2023). Non invasive decay analysis of monument using deep learning techniques. *Traitement du Signal*, 40(2), 639. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.18280/ts.400222>
23. Perumal, R., & Venkatachalam, S. B. (2021). RETRACTED ARTICLE: Non invasive detection of moss and crack in monuments using image processing techniques. *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*, 12(5), 5277-5285. [10.1007/s12652-020-02006-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s12652-020-02006-x)
24. Pawar, P. Y., & Ainapure, B. S. (2023). Image dataset of Pune city historical places for degradation detection, classification, and restoration. *Data in Brief*, 51, 109794 doi: [10.1016/j.dib.2023.109794](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2023.109794)
25. Rajaramesh, G., Reddy, K. K., Reddy, D. S., & Saiteja, E. (2025). Automated Identification of Indian Heritage Monuments using VGG16-Based Convolutional Neural Networks. *Asian Journal of Research in Computer Science*, 18(5), 1-10. DOI: [10.9734/ajrcos/2025/v18i5635](https://doi.org/10.9734/ajrcos/2025/v18i5635)
26. Hatır, E., Korkanç, M., Schachner, A., & İnce, İ. (2021). The deep learning method applied to the detection and mapping of stone deterioration in open-air sanctuaries of the Hittite period in Anatolia. *Journal of Cultural Heritage*, 51, 37-49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2021.07.004>
27. Pi, Y., Nath, N. D., & Behzadan, A. H. (2020). Convolutional neural networks for object detection in aerial imagery for disaster response and recovery. *Advanced Engineering Informatics*, 43, 101009. DOI:[10.1016/j.aei.2019.101009](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aei.2019.101009)
28. Wang, N., Zhao, X., Wang, L., & Zou, Z. (2019). Novel system for rapid investigation and damage detection in cultural heritage conservation based on deep learning. *Journal of Infrastructure Systems*, 25(3), 04019020. DOI:[10.1061/\(ASCE\)IS.1943-555X.0000499](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)IS.1943-555X.0000499)
29. Wan, J., Liu, L., Wang, H., Li, L., Li, W., Kou, S., & Hao, R. (2024). UNSCT-HRNet: Modeling Anatomical Uncertainty for Landmark Detection in Total Hip Arthroplasty. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2411.08488*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2411.08488>
30. Shukla, J. S., & Pandya, R. J. (2023). Deep learning-oriented c-GAN models for vegetative drought prediction on peninsular india. *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing*, 17, 282-297. DOI: [10.1109/JSTARS.2023.3328299](https://doi.org/10.1109/JSTARS.2023.3328299)